

Descriptor: *Six-Month Monitoring Dataset From a Ten-Turbine Onshore Wind Farm in Greece (SMD10TOWFGR)*

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ABSTRACT This article presents a detailed description of a dataset derived from the supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system of an onshore wind farm located in Greece, collected over a six-month monitoring period (1 January 2020–30 June 2020). In addition, it provides the source code and scripts implemented for data treatment. The dataset comprises approximately 26 000 measurements from 131 sensors and 24 000 event log entries per turbine across ten wind turbines (WTs). The sensors are categorized into 12 main categories: Generation, Gear, Nacelle, Rotor, Ambient, Grid, Controller, Blade, HV Transformer, Hour Counters, and Power Metrics, offering a comprehensive view of turbine performance and environmental conditions. Key parameters include pitch angle, power output, generator speed, and bearing temperature, alongside detailed event data such as extreme wind direction and alarm logs. The data were collected through an infrastructure that included sensors, data loggers, interfaces supporting protocols for data accessing and exchange, and a centralized SCADA database. Quality assessments ensured accuracy and consistency, with measures to standardize parameters, correct timestamp errors, and flag missing values. This dataset is designed to support applications such as wind energy forecasting, real-time operational monitoring, and predictive maintenance model development, providing a valuable resource for advancing research and operational improvements in renewable energy management.

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BACKGROUND

Wind farms (WFs), convert kinetic energy from wind into electrical power. A typical WF setup includes multiple wind turbines (WTs) arranged strategically to capture the optimal wind flow. Each turbine has several components, such as blades, a generator, a gearbox, and a control system. To monitor critical components and ensure efficient operation,

reliability, and safety, the WT is equipped with sensors that track critical performance variables. The sensors generate electrical signals, which are then translated into digital data regarding WT performance, environmental conditions, and health of individual components. The data presented here originate from a six-month monitoring period (1 January 2020–30 June 2020) at an onshore WF, comprising 10

WTs. This dataset, stored in the supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system, includes high-frequency operational parameters essential for assessing and optimizing turbine performance. Key data points cover variables such as pitch angle, power output, wind speed, and component health indicators. The dataset offers insights into real-time operational performance, allowing WF operators to adjust turbine settings, in response to volatile wind conditions. It also provides operational events and alarms recorded during that period, which can be used to analyze defective occurrences and assess the condition of the WTs. Apart from enabling monitoring of the equipment's health this dataset can potentially be reused for other applications. For instance, the dataset can be applied in performance statistical analysis to detect data trends and anomalies or in training machine learning (ML) algorithms to predict faults in turbine components, supporting condition monitoring and minimizing unexpected breakdowns through predictive maintenance models. Although the topic of predictive maintenance of WTs is of great importance, there are few publicly available SCADA datasets. Various overviews have summarized datasets available for WF analysis, covering aspects such as turbine capacities and monitoring systems [1], [2]. Several relevant datasets are described briefly below, with a particular focus on those that include SCADA data. One dataset includes two years of SCADA records from five offshore WTs [3]. While the dataset is suitable for unsupervised early anomaly detection, its limitations make it less ideal for supervised classification of specific faults. Another large dataset comprises data from three different wind farms; however, the anonymization of sensor names significantly limits its applicability for developing and training predictive maintenance models [4]. Other available dataset lacks both licensing information and variable descriptions, which constrains its usability [5]. Access to operational data from offshore WTs is available for universities and research institutions but require user registration and disclosure of data use [6]. Another set of data series from 12 WTs offers data for a four-month period for 22 sensor readings; the data appear to be well-structured and precise, but the lack of context and descriptive information makes it difficult to fully assess their quality and relevance [7]. A recent SCADA dataset contains records from 12 WTs, each with 25 columns including timestamps, sensor readings, and logs [8]. While the dataset offers valuable information, it includes manually generated simulated data, and its accessibility is limited. The reviewed datasets offer important insights; however, they frequently lack detailed descriptions, completeness, and contextual information. The dataset presented here ensures high accuracy and consistency. It is publicly available, documented and structured in a way that facilitates research and operational improvements in WFs operation.

COLLECTION METHODS AND DESIGN

The data are generated from an onshore WF that is located on a Greek island and has been operational since 2009. The

FIG. 1. Data flow in the wind farm.

island is interconnected with the mainland Greece and the WF consists of 10 WTs. The WF's monitoring system (a network of hardware and software systems) continuously monitors, stores, and process operational data from each WT in the WF. Key components of this system include various sensors installed on the turbine as well as an OLE for Process Control (OPC) interface, an Open Database Connectivity (ODBC) interface, and a central SCADA database, all integrated within the control room where operations are monitored and controlled. These components each play a distinctive and significant role and work together to capture, transmit, process and store data for monitoring and analysis. The OPC interface acts as a protocol standard for real-time data communication, facilitating the collection and standardization of data transmitted from each sensor on the turbines. The ODBC interface allows external applications or services to access the SCADA's historical database, enabling further processing and analysis. The SCADA retrieves production and operational data from the WTs as well as alarms, events and status information for monitoring and permanent storage in the database. Fig. 1 presents the data flow from the turbine to the control room.

The data collection and transmission processes begin with the sensors. The sensors are measuring parameters such as wind speed, temperature, pitch angle, and other critical variables. These readings are sent to an internal data logger within each WT. The data logger compiles these sensor measurements, applies basic filtering, and organizes the data by parameter type. It aggregates certain metrics to provide summary values at 10-min intervals and transmits the data to a system that offers OPC interfaces, located in the wind farm's control room or in the control room of the MV/HV Substation that the WF is electrically connected to. There, the system collects data from all sensors across the turbines, converts it into a standardized format, and organizes it into specific categories (grid data, meteorological data, performance data, control data, status data, counters, and temperatures) and stores it in its historical database. External applications can access these data using the ODBC protocol, which provides a standardized interface for querying the SCADA database for reporting, analysis, or integration with

FIG. 2. Layered flow of data.

other systems. The system using the ODBC protocol ensures compatibility by enabling the SCADA system to access and update data in the SCADA database. The database management system processes query requests to retrieve or modify specific data points and ensures the reliable transmission of data. The operational and performance data from the SCADA system were collected through the vendor’s platform, which provides a user interface for accessing all the WT data. After logging in, the parameters were selected by category. At this stage, the operational data were downloaded iteratively, one WT at a time, due to the large data volume. The data were extracted in 10-min intervals, which is the standard resolution used for SCADA-based performance monitoring. Once the selection was complete, the dataset was generated and previewed within the platform to primarily assess data integrity. The data were then exported directly in Excel (.xlsx) format. The diagram in Fig. 2 presents the layered architecture of data flow within the WF’s infrastructure. Starting at Level 0, data are captured by field-level sensors and then are processed through the data loggers at Level 1. As the data progress to Level 2 they are aggregated and stored within SCADA systems. At Level 3, processed information is made available in the business network supporting visualization and decision-making.

The data presented in this study were collected from the SCADA system over a six-month period (1 January 2020–30 June 2020). For each WT, more than 300 values were recorded in the central database every 10 min. The dataset comprises approximately 26 000 measurements for 131 sensors and 24 000 event log entries for each of the 10 WTs. Data points, where applicable, were collected as minimum, maximum, average, and variance or standard deviation values for each 10-min interval. The collected data were exported in .csv format, with each column representing a specific measurement. It was then processed and cleaned to ensure accuracy and consistency. A consolidated version of the dataset was created in Excel format, integrating data from all WTs. Additionally, alarm logs were incorporated into the consolidated version to provide a unified view of all 10 WTs, enabling comprehensive analysis and informed decision-making. In the original production data, certain timestamps were incorrect; however, only the date was recorded, rather than both date and time. This led to incomplete or inaccurate

entries for those data points. To correct these timestamps, we used the information from neighboring timestamps and the known 10-min interval between consecutive entries. As presented in the subsequent chapter, the dataset exhibits a low level of missing data, with less than 0.68% missing values across all WTs. By referencing adjacent timestamps, we were able to reconstruct missing time values and ensure that the corrected timestamps adhered to the expected 10-min intervals. The corrected timestamp format is “month/day/year hour.” Additionally, sensor column names across all WTs were standardized to ensure consistency. For example, the column name “WTG01_Generator RPM Max. (1)” was simplified to “Generator RPM Max.,” omitting the specific reference to WTG01. The number (1) indicated the order of data collection, which varied by WT. In a subsequent step, column names were further updated to include metric units in square brackets; for example, “Nacelle Temp. Avg.” was changed to “Nacelle Temp. Avg. [°C].” There are various methods for filling missing cell values, such as forward fill, backward fill, interpolation, or using a constant value [9], [10]. However, because the appropriate method depends not only on the data type in each column but also on the data’s intended use, we chose not to fill any missing cells at this stage. Instead, we added a “missing data” column, indicating if a timestamp is available but any sensor data are missing. It should be noted that available sensors are calibrated according to the manufacturer’s instructions to ensure data accuracy.

VALIDATION AND QUALITY

We have enhanced each WT’s dataset by including a comprehensive statistical analysis for each individual .csv file containing the operational data. The statistical analysis was based on the python module *ydata-profiling* [11] and covered various parameters such as extreme and mean values recorded by sensors that measure parameters such as wind speed, power output, rotor speed, and temperature. The statistical analysis for each WT is stored in HTML reports; all related reports are available through an open GitHub repository [12], making them easily accessible via browser. In Fig. 3, a temperature-distribution histogram of a specific temperature sensor is exemplary presented.

We analyzed the missing values in the various recorded sensor datasets of the WTs, which are summarized in Table I.

Half of the WTs have less than 0.1% missing values. WT03 has the highest number of missing values, with 850 missing entries (3.2%). Overall, the data quality is high, as only a small number of values are missing. Data consistency was ensured by verifying the accuracy of timestamps, confirming that sensor values fell within expected ranges, and by identifying outliers to address any abnormal or extreme values that could indicate sensor errors or unusual operating conditions. Operational logs, comprising 230 618 events and alarms across all 10 WTs, were analyzed and curated for insights. These logs are classified into four types:

FIG. 3. Histogram of the generator bearing temperature of WTG01.

TABLE I. Overview of the Amount of Missing Data for the Different WTs in Absolute Numbers and in Percent

WT No.	Missing Values	Missing Values in Percent (%)
1	7	<0.1
2	10	<0.1
3	850	3.2
4	2	<0.1
5	619	2.4
6	31	0.1
7	143	0.5
8	36	0.1
9	4	<0.1
10	11	<0.1

- 1) *system log (S)*;
- 2) *warning log (W)*;
- 3) *operation log (O)*;
- 4) *alarm log (A)*.

The “Operational log” event type is by far the most dominant, accounting for nearly 98.5% of all events. However, the most relevant type for prognostic health management is the “Alarm log” which has 1002 entries (0.43% of all data). These alarms are analyzed in detail due to their importance for predictive maintenance and operational safety. Approximately 60 unique codes are associated with the “Alarm log” revealing specific operational challenges and environmental impacts. Below are the ten most frequent alarms, alongside their implications for WT performance and safety.

- 1) 102: Emergency circuit open.
- 2) 620: Defect Pitch Accumulator C:69.
- 3) 879: EMERGENCY after signal error.
- 4) 604: Low Press pitchblock C 171bar.
- 5) 100: Too many auto-restarts: 3.
- 6) 356: Extreme wind direction.
- 7) 509: Ext. high wind speed.
- 8) 62: Ground status report timeout.
- 9) 942: Leakage pitch accumulated C: 22bar.
- 10) 745: Error azimuth angle.

The “102: Emergency Circuit Open” alarm indicates that the safety mechanism has been likely triggered causing an interruption in the emergency circuit. As a result, the WT

TABLE II. Key Parameters Thresholds

Parameters	Unit	Thresholds	
		Min	Max
Generator Bearing Temp. Avg.	°C	-20	140
Generator Bearing2 Temp. Avg.		-20	105
Gear Bearing Temp. Avg.		25	90
Gear Oil Temp. Avg.		5	-
Rotor	rpm	-	134

is probably out of operation and the power may be lost to essential systems for turbine operation, until the issue is resolved. Another severe alarm is the “879: EMERGENCY after Signal Error,” which indicates that an emergency stop has been triggered to prevent potential damage or unsafe operating conditions. A frequent alarm, “356: Extreme wind direction,” suggests that the turbine often encounters wind coming from directions outside its optimal alignment, which could affect the safe and efficient operation of the turbine. Similarly, “509: External high wind speed” indicates that the turbine frequently shuts down due to high wind speeds, a standard safety measure during extreme weather. It is worth noting that the cut-in wind speed of the WTGs is 4 m/s and the cutout wind speed is 25 m/s. Several alarms focus on issues with the pitch control system, which adjusts the blade angles to optimize power generation. As an example are the “942: Leakage pitch accumulated, C: 22bar” and “604: Low pressure in pitch block C 171bar” alarms; the first points to a failure of the accumulator in the hydraulic pitch system, while the second indicates a low-pressure issue within the hydraulic pitch block. Both alarms indicate hydraulic issues affecting the pitch mechanism. Leakages and low-pressure readings suggest possible fluid loss or pressure instability within the hydraulic system. Additionally, “620: Defect Pitch Accumulator C: 69” indicates that a pitch accumulator, essential for storing hydraulic energy for quick blade adjustments, is defective. During the effectiveness of this alarm, the WT may be unable to safely adjust its blades position during an emergency or a power failure. This poses a significant risk to both WT’s performance and safety. The logs also show problems with yaw alignment and emergency systems. “745: Error azimuth angle” refers to an issue with the azimuth alignment, meaning the turbine may not always be facing the optimal direction. Alarms such as “102: Emergency circuit open” suggest recurring emergency stops, possibly triggered by safety-related signal errors. Alarm “62: Ground status report timeout” indicates that the system is unable to receive status reports from the ground or grounding system within a specified time. The less severe alarm is “100: Too many auto-restarts: 3.” After three automatic restarts, the WT is unable to resume normal operation on its own and manual acknowledgment of the fault is required. Furthermore, we filtered the sensor data- and partly the status information- to identify potential outliers. To do so, we applied two approaches. In the first approach, we used vendor-provided alarm thresholds for five key parameters. Table II presents these parameters and their respective thresholds.

This analysis did not identify any outliers in the WTs. As a second approach we filtered the data using a Hampel filter [13]. This filter applies a sliding window across the time series, compares each data point to the local median within that window, and flags points that deviate beyond a specified threshold as outliers. The filter was applied univariately to each of the 128 columns of the sensor data and status information. Outliers are indicated with a value of 1 in newly added columns, each corresponding to an original sensor data column. A value of 0 represents a normal data point, while a 1 means that the Hampel filter has identified it as an outlier. The analysis indicates that outliers represent between 4.11% and 4.46% of the data across all cases. All results are presented in an Excel file, titled “Scada_moniotring_outliers_2020” under an open GitHub repository [14]. The Hampel analysis is included in new columns, preserving the original data while flagging potential outliers. No values have been removed, as outlier handling should be performed by the user based on the specific task.

RECORDS AND STORAGE

The consolidated version of the dataset described in this article consists of 20 tabs in total. Ten tabs contain sensor readings for each turbine and ten tabs provide the issue logs for all recorded events for each WT. Each tab has a unique identifier in the form WTxx_data.csv for the sensor readings, and WTxx_logs.csv for the alarms and event logs, where xx represents the turbine number (ranging from 1 to 10). Regarding the sensors reading tabs, the file contains raw sensor data captured every 10 min, offering a granular view of each WT’s operational performance. The number of rows measured per sensor equals 26 208 for the first six months of 2020. It is worth mentioning that for WT03, approximately 2300 measurements are missing due to technical issues that caused the generation to be down for 17 days. Each tab contains 104 columns for sensor data and 27 columns for status information. In addition, the first column provides information about the timestamp with the first one being 1 January 2020 12:00:00 am and the last 30 June 2020 11:59:59 pm. Although, the sensors’ readings are not categorized within the file, for better understanding, we have group them into 12 basic categories. Table III provides an overview of each category with the number of available metrics. The metrics contain different types of measurements, such as maximum, minimum, absolute, average, standard deviation, or raw values without aggregation. The type of measurement depends on the component or physical quantity being recorded.

It is worth noting that the outlier tabs [14] use the same column names as the corresponding data tabs, allowing for easy alignment between them. The log tabs include event and alarm data summarized daily, if occurred, for each WT. These tabs capture operational events, alarms, and their timestamps, along with metadata on the duration and type of each event. Each of these tabs follows the column structure presented in Table IV.

TABLE III. Sensor Reading Categories on Dataset

Sensor Category	Description	Number of Metrics
Generator Metrics	Monitor the generator’s rotational performance and temperature to ensure stable power production.	11
Gear Metrics	Provide insights into the internal mechanics of the gearbox to prevent wear and failure.	9
Nacelle Metrics	Track the structural conditions of the nacelle, which is the housing that contains all the generating components in a wind turbine.	2
Rotor Metrics	Monitor the performance and structural integrity of the rotor.	4
Ambient Metrics	Measure the ambient surrounding conditions, such as temperature, wind speed and direction, that directly impact turbine energy generation.	8
Grid Metrics	Focus on the interface between the turbine’s output and the electrical grid.	33
Controller Metrics	Monitor internal turbine temperatures and control stability.	6
Blade Metrics	Monitor the pitch angle and spinner temperature.	6
HV Tranfo Metrics	Monitors the air outlet temperature and each phase temperature within the high-voltage transformer.	4
Power Metrics	Measures the active and reactive power outputs across generator components.	5
Hour Counters (Status Info)	Record cumulative hours for turbine states to support maintenance planning.	23
System Logs and Alarms (Status Info)	Capture system alerts that may indicate emerging issues.	4

TABLE IV. Contents of Alarms and Events Log Tabs

Field	Description
Code	Internal code associated with the specific event or alarm
Description	Message describing the event or alarm
Detected	Timestamp recording the moment each event or alarm was triggered
Device ack (Acknowledgment)	Alarms requiring acknowledgment record the timestamp when acknowledgment is made
Reset/Run	Timestamp indicating the moment an alarm is reset or operation resumes
Duration	For alarms, this field records the time from detection to reset in hours, minutes, and seconds
Event Type	Identifies the log type (operation, system, alarm, or warning)
Severity	Integer from 1 to 1000 indicating the severity level of the event

The SCADA system categorizes alarms and warnings based on their severity level, with the categorization of personal safety alarms being the most critical for the WT. Communication errors are assigned a moderate level of severity. Additionally, WT alarms are further classified by how they need to be acknowledged. There are two categories for these alarms, those requiring local acknowledgment and those that can be acknowledged remotely or automatically.

The first ones have a higher severity, while the second ones have progressively lower severity. Other WT related events fall into the least severe category.

INSIGHTS AND NOTES

This dataset, with its detailed documentation and structure, is a valuable resource for a wide range of advanced applications. Emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI)-driven anomaly detection and adaptive turbine control algorithms, provide new avenues to leverage this dataset for advancing wind farm operations. The dataset can also be used to analyze turbine efficiency, identify performance issues, and support the development of predictive maintenance models- an important area in the wind energy sector where publicly available SCADA datasets remain limited. In addition to predictive maintenance, researchers can also utilize this dataset for general time-series analysis or develop sophisticated hybrid models that integrate SCADA data with meteorological forecasts, leading to more accurate energy output predictions. These insights contribute to the enhancement of operational strategies and the development of innovative methods to improve turbine reliability and efficiency. Moreover, the dataset can be used to develop digital twin models for simulation-based testing and optimization of turbine performance in various scenarios. Algorithms for optimizing turbine parameters, such as pitch control under varying wind conditions, can be developed and validated against historical data. Additionally, operators can use data for benchmarking key performance indicators (KPIs) such as capacity factor and power efficiency across turbines. Furthermore, the historical alarms and operational data are essential for grid integration studies, ensuring that the WTs contribute effectively to grid stability. These applications ultimately facilitate the continuous improvement of WF operations.

SOURCE CODE AND SCRIPTS

All source code and scripts are openly available to ensure full transparency and facilitate understanding for data users [15]. Additionally, the software used to calculate statistics, along with all required Python module dependencies, is provided to enable seamless reproducibility. The statistical analysis in this project is conducted using *ydata-profiling* [11] which provides an in-depth and automated approach to exploratory data analysis, allowing for efficient profiling of the dataset's key metrics and patterns. In addition, the developed software depends on the following python libraries:

- 1) `ydata-profiling==4.16.1`;
- 2) `pandas==2.2.3`;
- 3) `matplotlib==3.10.0`;
- 4) `seaborn==0.13.2`;
- 5) `numpy==2.1.3`.

The Python version is 3.12.8 and a detailed list of all dependencies is provided in the *pyproject.toml* file, following

the format standardized by Python Enhancement Proposal 518 [16].

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A.N. served as the main author and reviewed the prepared dataset. A.W. and S.V. curated, analyzed, and prepared the data for publication, contributing to the manuscript's writing. S.T. and P.P. reviewed the manuscript, providing feedback and edits. All authors contributed to and reviewed the final manuscript.

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